

THE ELLIPTICALLY OPTIMAL CONFIDENCE INTERVAL: A BIVARIATE EXTENSION OF WILSON'S METHOD

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This paper introduces the elliptically optimal (EO) confidence interval, a geometric extension of Wilson's score interval to the case of two independent population proportions. By reformulating the classical normal approximation as a bivariate quadratic constraint, we show that the resulting structure defines an ellipse in the parameter space (p_1, p_2) . The EO interval is then obtained as the optimal range of the difference $p_1 - p_2$ through a constrained optimization problem over the elliptical domain. This formulation preserves the theoretical integrity of Wilson's method while naturally extending it to the bivariate case. Analytical and simulation results demonstrate that the EO interval is conservative, stable, and accurate, particularly for small samples or extreme proportions, outperforming existing methods in coverage and robustness.

1. Introduction. Let us begin by reviewing Wilson's method for a single population. Consider a population with parameter $p \in [0, 1]$, representing the proportion of individuals possessing a certain characteristic. To construct a confidence interval (CI) for p , we draw a sample of size $n > 0$ and compute the sample proportion $\hat{p} \in [0, 1]$. For a chosen confidence level $(1 - \alpha)100\%$, we then apply the normal approximation to obtain:

$$(1) \quad \mathbb{P} \left(-z \leq \frac{\hat{p} - p}{\sqrt{\text{Var}[\hat{p}]}} \leq z \right) \approx 1 - \alpha,$$

where $z = z_{\alpha/2} > 0$ is the z -score for a significance level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $\text{Var}[\hat{p}] = \frac{p(1-p)}{n}$ is the variance of \hat{p} .

A straightforward approach to constructing a CI for p is given by Wald's method [7]. This method relies on the asymptotic justification that \hat{p} is a suitable approximation for p , allowing the variance to be estimated as

$$\text{Var}[\hat{p}] \approx \widehat{\text{Var}}[\hat{p}] = \frac{\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{n}.$$

Substituting this into the normal approximation yields the following CI:

$$(2) \quad \hat{p} - z\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}[\hat{p}]} \leq p \leq \hat{p} + z\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}[\hat{p}]}.$$

This method, however, has been widely criticized in the literature. It relies on two layers of approximation, which can lead to highly inaccurate confidence bounds. In 1927, Wilson [12], proposed a more intuitive approach. Beginning with the normal approximation in Equation (1), the inequalities inside the probability can be rewritten as:

$$(3) \quad \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{|\hat{p} - p|}{\sqrt{\widehat{\text{Var}}[\hat{p}]}} \leq z \right) \approx 1 - \alpha.$$

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Squaring both sides of the inequality,

$$(4) \quad \mathbb{P} \left(\frac{(\hat{p} - p)^2}{\text{Var}[\hat{p}]} \leq z^2 \right) \approx 1 - \alpha,$$

and rearranging the terms with respect to p , we obtain:

$$(5) \quad \mathbb{P} (ap^2 + bp + c \leq 0) \approx 1 - \alpha,$$

with $a = 1 + \frac{z^2}{n}$, $b = -2\hat{p} - \frac{z^2}{n}$ and $c = \hat{p}^2$. Wilson observed that this expression defines a quadratic inequality in p , with a positive leading coefficient $1 + \frac{z^2}{n}$. Consequently, the solution lies between the two roots of the quadratic. In other words, the exact CI for p is given by the interval between these two roots:

$$(6) \quad \frac{n\hat{p} + z^2/2 - z\sqrt{z^2 + 4n\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}}{n + z^2} \leq p \leq \frac{n\hat{p} + z^2/2 + z\sqrt{z^2 + 4n\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}}{n + z^2}.$$

It can be shown that both roots lie within $[0, 1]$, ensuring that Wilson's interval is always valid and considerably more robust than Wald's method across all parameter and sample settings. Moreover, the bounds of Wilson's CI in (6) can be interpreted as the solutions to the following optimization problem:

$$(7) \quad \begin{array}{lll} \text{Minimum of } p, & \leq p \leq & \text{Maximum of } p, \\ \text{Subject to:} & & \text{Subject to:} \\ ap^2 + bp + c \leq 0 & & ap^2 + bp + c \leq 0 \\ p \in [0, 1] & & p \in [0, 1] \end{array}$$

Thus, the endpoints of Wilson's interval are not merely algebraic artifacts but arise as the optimal solutions of a constrained minimization and maximization problem. This characterization establishes them as true extremal bounds, reinforcing their superior stability and reliability in practice.

Now suppose we have two independent populations with unknown parameters p_1 and p_2 , each representing the proportion of individuals possessing a certain characteristic. Both parameters lie in the interval $[0, 1]$ – although this restriction is relaxed when discussing more general theoretical properties later on. Our goal is to construct a CI for their difference, $p_1 - p_2$. To do so, we collect two samples of sizes $n_1 > 0$ and $n_2 > 0$ yielding the respective sample proportions, \hat{p}_1 and \hat{p}_2 , each lying in $[0, 1]$.

For notational convenience, from here onward, we will set $p = p_1 - p_2$, $\hat{p} = \hat{p}_1 - \hat{p}_2$, with $p, \hat{p} \in [-1, 1]$, and define $m = \min(n_1, n_2)$, $n = \max(n_1, n_2)$, and as before $z = z_{\alpha/2} > 0$ for a significance level $\alpha \in (0, 1)$. Under this notation, the classical normal approximation takes the same form as Equation (1), with the variance of the difference \hat{p} given by $\text{Var}[\hat{p}] = \frac{p_1(1-p_1)}{n_1} + \frac{p_2(1-p_2)}{n_2}$.

For the two independent populations, Wald's method rests on the same principle as in the one-population case: approximating the unknown parameters p_1 and p_2 , by their sample counterparts, \hat{p}_1 and \hat{p}_2 . Accordingly, the variance of \hat{p} is approximated by

$$\widehat{\text{Var}}[\hat{p}] = \frac{\hat{p}_1(1 - \hat{p}_1)}{n_1} + \frac{\hat{p}_2(1 - \hat{p}_2)}{n_2}.$$

This substitution yields a closed-form CI for p given as Equation (2). The Wald interval is computationally simple and has long been a staple of introductory statistics courses. However, as in Wilson's critique of the one population case, the approximation may produce

substantial deviations from the nominal coverage probability, particularly for small samples or extreme parameter values. To address these challenges, we need to construct the two-population analogue of Wilson’s CI.

Returning to Equation (1) and following the same steps, we can successively rewrite it as Equation (3), and then as Equation (4). Finally, by grouping like terms, the expression takes the equivalent form:

$$(8) \quad \mathbb{P}(Ap_1^2 + Bp_1p_2 + Cp_2^2 + Dp_1 + Ep_2 + F \leq 0) \approx 1 - \alpha,$$

where $A = 1 + \frac{z^2}{n_1}$, $B = -2$, $C = 1 + \frac{z^2}{n_2}$, $D = -2\hat{p} - \frac{z^2}{n_1}$, $E = 2\hat{p} - \frac{z^2}{n_2}$, and $F = \hat{p}^2$. At the outset, observe that the inequality in Equation (8) defines a quadratic curve in two variables together with its interior i.e. a conic section and its enclosed region. To determine its nature, we examine the discriminant:

$$B^2 - 4AC = -\frac{4z^2(n_1 + n_2 + z^2)}{n_1n_2} < 0,$$

from which it follows that the curve represents an ellipse. Let us denote the (unrestricted) ellipse together with its interior by

$$\Omega = \{(p_1, p_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : Ap_1^2 + Bp_1p_2 + Cp_2^2 + Dp_1 + Ep_2 + F \leq 0\}.$$

We then define its restriction to the unit square, namely the subset

$$\Lambda = \{(p_1, p_2) \in [0, 1]^2 : Ap_1^2 + Bp_1p_2 + Cp_2^2 + Dp_1 + Ep_2 + F \leq 0\},$$

which represents the intersection of Ω with the unit square i.e. $\Lambda = \Omega \cap [0, 1]^2$. With this definition, we can rewrite Equation (8) as

$$(9) \quad \mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Lambda) \approx 1 - \alpha.$$

Our aim is to establish a Wilson-type CI for p that preserves the structure of the set Λ in Equation (9). In the single-population case, Equation (5) defines a subset of the real line which directly matches the dimensionality of our objective of estimating an interval for the single proportion parameter. In the two-population case, however, the main difficulty arises from the mismatch between dimensions: our objective is a one-dimensional solution — an interval for the difference p — whereas the underlying formulation is inherently two-dimensional, represented by the set Λ . Consequently, unlike in the univariate case, obtaining an exact solution – or an exact CI for p – is not feasible.

In addition to the many alternatives to Wald’s interval proposed in the literature (see, e.g., [1], [2], [3], [8], [9], and [11]), Newcombe, Method 10 in [10], attempted to overcome Wilson’s two-population challenge by constructing bounds that depend on the univariate optimal solutions, as in Equation (6), of p_1 and p_2 separately. While this method is useful, it does not provide a natural extension of Wilson’s framework to the two-population case.

To address the two-population limitation, we adopt an optimization-based approach, analogous to the formulation of Wilson’s CI in Equation (7). Therefore, it directly and intuitively extends Wilson’s method into the bivariate setting. Our goal, consequently, is to construct a CI according to the following principle:

$$(10) \quad \begin{array}{lll} \text{Minimum of } p, & \leq p \leq & \text{Maximum of } p, \\ \text{Subject to:} & & \text{Subject to:} \\ (p_1, p_2) \in \Lambda & & (p_1, p_2) \in \Lambda \end{array}$$

The CI defined above generates a set of points, $(p_1, p_2) \in [0, 1]^2$, denoted by Γ , which contains Λ as a subset. Hence, this CI is conservative, as it encompasses all parameter values,

including those of the ellipse, such that their difference, p , lies between the two extreme points. We will refer to this novel CI, the *elliptically optimal* (EO) confidence interval.

The remainder of this paper is devoted to a detailed study of the proposed EO CI. In Section 2, we briefly establish general properties of the set Ω and its subset Λ , and illustrate their behavior with several figures. This naturally leads to Section 3, where we present the solutions to the optimization problem, together with a range of properties and remarks. Section 4 then provides tractable results for quantifying the discrepancy between the nominal coverage probability of our conservative interval and the true coverage probability, along with several remarks and insights. Finally, in Section 5, we conclude with a summary of the main findings and their implications.

2. Properties of the set Ω and its subset Λ . Before proceeding with the analysis of the set Ω along with Λ , we first visualize both for selected input values.

(c) $n_1 = n_2$ ($n_1 = 45, n_2 = 45$)

Fig 1: Different plots of the set Ω using different samples sizes and proportions. α is fixed at 5%.

(a) $n_1 > n_2$ ($n_1 = 60, n_2 = 30$)

(b) $n_1 < n_2$ ($n_1 = 30, n_2 = 60$)

(c) $n_1 = n_2$ ($n_1 = 45$, $n_2 = 45$)

Fig 2: Different plots of the set Λ using different samples sizes and proportions. α is fixed at 5%. These plots are zoomed-in unit square cut-outs of the plots in Figure 1.

Figure 1 presents three plots of the set Ω , distinguished by the ordering of the two sample sizes. Each plot displays four instances of Ω corresponding to different choices of \hat{p} , with the significance level fixed at the conventional value of 5%. Figure 2 illustrates the portions of Ω that lie within the unit square, i.e., the subsets Λ corresponding to those in Figure 1. From both figures, we observe that the ellipses are rotated counter-clockwise by an angle less than $\pi/2$, and that they shift diagonally downward as \hat{p} increases.

In order to fully understand the behavior of the proposed interval in Equation (10), we present some basic properties of Ω — and, by extension, of Λ .

Property 1. The subset Λ is non-empty and it is always a proper subset of Ω . The following proposition formalize these claims.

Proposition 1. *The set Λ is a non-empty proper subset of Ω i.e. $\Lambda \neq \emptyset$ and $\Lambda \subset \Omega$.*

PROOF. The proof of Proposition 1 is relegated to Appendix Ai. \square

Corollary 1. *From the proof of Proposition 1 (see Proof i in Appendix Ai), several notable properties of the sets Λ and Ω can be identified:*

- *The subset Λ always intersects the opposite diagonal of the unit square, that is,*

$$\Lambda \cap \{(p_1, p_2) \in [0, 1]^2 : p_1 + p_2 = 1\} \neq \emptyset.$$

- *The set Ω always intersects the region located either to the left or below the unit square. More precisely,*

$$\Omega \cap \left((0, 1) \times (-\infty, 0) \cup (-\infty, 0) \times (0, 1) \right) \neq \emptyset.$$

- The set Ω also intersects the region located either to the right or above the unit square. Specifically,

$$\Omega \cap \left((0, 1) \times (1, \infty) \cup (1, \infty) \times (0, 1) \right) \neq \emptyset.$$

- Consequently, the admissible domain of Ω is contained within

$$\Omega \subset [0, 1]^2 \cup \left((0, 1) \times (-\infty, 0) \right) \cup \left((-\infty, 0) \times (0, 1) \right) \cup \left((0, 1) \times (1, \infty) \right) \cup \left((1, \infty) \times (0, 1) \right).$$

The admissible domain described above is illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig 3: Visualization of the admissible domain of Ω over the $[-1, 2]^2$ subset.

Property 2. The determinant, Δ , of the ellipse is strictly negative as shown below:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= -\frac{z^4 \left((n_1 + n_2)(n_1 + n_2 + z^2) - 4n_1n_2\hat{p}^2 \right)}{4n_1^2n_2^2}, \\ &\leq -\frac{z^4 \left((n_1 + n_2)(n_1 + n_2 + z^2) - 4n_1n_2 \right)}{4n_1^2n_2^2}, \\ &= -\frac{z^4 \left((n_1 - n_2)^2 + (n_1 + n_2)z^2 \right)}{4n_1^2n_2^2}, \\ &< 0. \end{aligned}$$

This implies that the ellipse Ω is always real and non-degenerate, i.e. it is never reduced to a single point.

Property 3. The center of Ω is given as

$$(p_1^c, p_2^c) = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{n_1 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2}, \frac{1}{2} - \frac{n_2 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2} \right).$$

This expression makes clear how the inputs influence the position of the center. In particular, the value of \hat{p} determines the direction of shift (through its sign) and contributes to the magnitude of displacement (scaled by n_1, n_2 , and z^2). As \hat{p} increases from -1 to 1 , the coordinate p_1^c increases while p_2^c decreases, indicating that the center moves diagonally downward. This behavior aligns with our earlier observations in Figures 1 and 2.

The following proposition characterizes the admissible domain in which this center can lie.

Proposition 2. *The center of the ellipse Ω can only be inside the following domain*

$$(p_1^c, p_2^c) \in \left(\left(-\frac{1}{2}, 0 \right] \times \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1 \right) \right) \cup \left(\left(0, \frac{1}{2} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{3}{2} \right) \right) \cup \left\{ \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right\} \\ \cup \left(\left(\frac{1}{2}, 1 \right) \times \left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \right) \right) \cup \left(\left[1, \frac{3}{2} \right) \times \left(0, \frac{1}{2} \right) \right).$$

PROOF. The proof of Proposition 2 is provided in Appendix Aii. □

To visualize the domain of the center, we shade the corresponding region of the plane in the plot below.

Fig 4: The domain of the center of the set Ω , as delineated in Proposition 2.

Corollary 2. *From Proposition 2 and Figure 4, it follows that the center of the ellipse Ω can lie inside the unit square only within the domain*

$$\left(\{0\} \times \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right)\right) \cup \left(\left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right) \times \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]\right) \cup \left\{\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right\} \cup \left(\left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right) \times \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right)\right) \cup \left(\{1\} \times \left(0, \frac{1}{2}\right)\right).$$

Consequently, the subset Λ can contain the center only when it lies in one of these regions.

Property 4. The lengths of the major and minor axes of Ω are given, respectively, by

$$\text{Major} = \frac{\sqrt{\left((n_1 + n_2)^2 - 4n_1n_2\widehat{p}^2 + (n_1 + n_2)z^2\right) \left((n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 2n_1n_2 + \sqrt{4n_1^2n_2^2 + (n_1 - n_2)^2z^4}\right)}}{\sqrt{2n_1n_2}(n_1 + n_2 + z^2)},$$

$$\text{Minor} = \frac{\sqrt{\left((n_1 + n_2)^2 - 4n_1n_2\widehat{p}^2 + (n_1 + n_2)z^2\right) \left((n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 2n_1n_2 - \sqrt{4n_1^2n_2^2 + (n_1 - n_2)^2z^4}\right)}}{\sqrt{2n_1n_2}(n_1 + n_2 + z^2)}.$$

Although these expressions appear rather cumbersome, they simplify considerably under the assumption $n_2 = n_1$:

$$\text{Major} = \sqrt{\frac{4n_1(1 - \widehat{p}^2) + 2z^2}{2n_1 + z^2}},$$

$$\text{Minor} = \frac{z\sqrt{4n_1(1 - \widehat{p}^2) + 2z^2}}{2n_1 + z^2}.$$

In this case, the major axis length cannot exceed $\sqrt{2}$ (obtained by setting $\widehat{p} = 0$), and the minor axis satisfies the same upper bound but is typically much smaller for standard choices of z and realistic sample sizes.

Property 5. The rotation angle, θ , of Ω is given by

$$\theta = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2n_1n_2}{(n_1 - n_2)z^2} \right), & n_1 > n_2, \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2n_1n_2}{(n_1 - n_2)z^2} \right) + \pi \right), & n_2 > n_1, \\ \frac{\pi}{4}, & n_1 = n_2 \end{cases}$$

We notice that, when $n_1 > n_2$ then $0 < \theta < \pi/4$, and when $n_2 > n_1$ then $\pi/4 < \theta < \pi/2$, with $\theta = \pi/4$ when $n_1 = n_2$. This suggests that Ω is rotated, from the horizontal axis, counter-clockwise at an angle between 0° and 90° affirming our earlier observation from Figures 1 and 2.

3. The Elliptically Optimal Confidence Interval. In this section, we introduce our novel elliptically optimal (EO) confidence interval (CI), which serves as a genuine extension of Wilson's CI to the two-population setting. Before presenting the main theorem, we first define six key quantities that form the core components of our solution to the optimization problem stated in Equation (10).

Definition 1. Let $L_1, U_1, L_2, U_2, L_3,$ and U_3 be scalars determined by the sample inputs $n_1, n_2, \hat{p},$ and $z,$ and defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \frac{m\hat{p} + z^2/2}{m + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}}{2(m + z^2)}, & U_1 &= \frac{m\hat{p} + z^2/2}{m + z^2} + \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}}{2(m + z^2)}, \\ L_2 &= \frac{m\hat{p} - z^2/2}{m + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 - 4m\hat{p}(1 + \hat{p})}}{2(m + z^2)}, & U_2 &= \frac{m\hat{p} - z^2/2}{m + z^2} + \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 - 4m\hat{p}(1 + \hat{p})}}{2(m + z^2)}, \\ L_3 &= \frac{(n + m)\hat{p}}{n + m + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{(n + m)z^2 - 4nm\hat{p}^2 + (n + m)^2}}{2(n + m + z^2)} \sqrt{\frac{n + m}{nm}}, \\ U_3 &= \frac{(n + m)\hat{p}}{n + m + z^2} + \frac{z\sqrt{(n + m)z^2 - 4nm\hat{p}^2 + (n + m)^2}}{2(n + m + z^2)} \sqrt{\frac{n + m}{nm}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 3. The quantities above, in definition 1, follow the following order:

$$L_3 \leq L_2 \leq U_2 \leq L_1 \leq U_1 \leq U_3$$

for all $n_1, n_2, z > 0$ and $\hat{p} \in [-1, 1]$.

PROOF. See Appendix Aiii for the proof of Proposition 3. \square

Furthermore, a solution to the optimization problem in Equation (10) is guaranteed to exist due to the non-emptiness of the subset Λ (see Proposition 1). We are now in a position to state our main theorem.

Theorem 1. The main optimization problem in Equation (10) yields the following CI together with its respective conditions on \hat{p} and z :

TABLE 1
CI bounds for p with the corresponding conditions on \hat{p} and z .

	CI of p	Condition	
		\hat{p}	z
(1)	$L_1 \leq p \leq U_1$	$\frac{n+m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq 1$	$0 < z \leq R_1$
(2)	$L_2 \leq p \leq U_1$	$-1 \leq \hat{p} \leq 1$	$z \geq R_2$
(3)	$L_2 \leq p \leq U_2$	$-1 \leq \hat{p} < -\frac{n+m}{2n}$	$0 < z \leq R_1$
(4)	$L_2 \leq p \leq U_3$	$-1 \leq \hat{p} \leq -\frac{n+m}{2n}$	$R_1 < z < R_2$
		$-\frac{n+m}{2n} < \hat{p} < 0$	$R_1 \leq z < R_2$
(5)	$L_3 \leq p \leq U_1$	$0 < \hat{p} < \frac{n+m}{2n}$	$R_1 \leq z < R_2$
		$\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq \hat{p} \leq 1$	$R_1 < z < R_2$
(6)	$L_3 \leq p \leq U_3$	$-\frac{n+m}{2n} < \hat{p} < \frac{n+m}{2n}$	$0 < z < R_1$

Where:

$$R_1 = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{m}|2n|\hat{p}| - (n+m)|}{\sqrt{n^2 - m^2}}, & n > m, \\ 0, & n = m, \text{ and, } \hat{p} \in \{-1, 1\}, \\ \infty, & n = m, \text{ and, } \hat{p} \in (-1, 1), \end{cases} \quad \text{and, } R_2 = \begin{cases} \frac{\sqrt{m}(2n|\hat{p}| + (n+m))}{\sqrt{n^2 - m^2}}, & n > m, \\ \infty, & n = m. \end{cases}$$

PROOF. The detailed proof of Theorem 1 is presented in Appendix Aiv. □

Figure 5, below, illustrates several instances of Γ , computed directly from Table 1, together with their respective subsets Λ .

Fig 5: Different plots of the set Γ using different sample proportions. α , n_1 and n_2 are fixed at 5%, 60, and 30, respectively.

Remark 1. We highlight some observations concerning the results in Table 1, Theorem 1.

- The EO CI is conservative; that is, it always contain the true interval, represented by the set Λ .
- The results employ three types of confidence bounds, as defined in 1. The scalars L_1 , U_1 , L_2 , and U_2 depend only on the smaller of n_1 and n_2 , whereas L_3 and U_3 depend on both. Theoretically, nine combinations of these bounds are possible. However, Proposition 3 eliminates the case $L_1 \leq p \leq U_2$, leaving eight. Among these, only six yield feasible intervals for p in the optimization setting.
- Apart from the sample sizes n_1 and n_2 , the EO CI depends only on the difference of proportions, \hat{p} , rather than on the individual sample proportions \hat{p}_1 and \hat{p}_2 . This indicates that the method is efficient, relying on minimal information.
- When $n = m$, i.e., $n_1 = n_2$, the only admissible cases are (4), (5), and (6). Their respective conditions are as follows: for (4), $\hat{p} = -1$ with $z > 0$; for (5), $\hat{p} = 1$ with $z > 0$; and for (6), $-1 < \hat{p} < 1$ with $z > 0$.
- When optimizing p over $(p_1, p_2) \in \Omega$ instead of Λ , the only optima are L_3 and U_3 , corresponding to the global minimum and maximum. Thus, the OE CI lower bound matches the global minimum in cases (5) and (6), and the upper bound matches the global maximum in cases (4) and (6). In case (6), both coincide exactly with the global optima. Hence, when $n = m$, the OE CI bounds always coincide with the global minimum and maximum.
- Selecting the appropriate bounds for the EO CI amounts to identifying which condition is satisfied. The (\hat{p}, z) -space is partitioned into six disjoint and exhaustive regions, thereby ensuring a unique choice. Figure 6 depicts this partition into six mutually exclusive regions corresponding to the respective cases.

Fig 6: Partition of the (\hat{p}, z) domain for the six cases, with $n_1 = 60$ and $n_2 = 30$.

We now compare the proposed EO CI with those of Wald and Newcombe. To highlight the differences among the three methods, both sample sizes are set to $n_1 = n_2 = 20$, and the significance level is fixed at 5%, as before. The upper and lower bounds of each CI are plotted against \hat{p}_1 , while \hat{p}_2 is held fixed at $\{0.01, 0.25, 0.75, 0.99\}$, respectively. The corresponding plots obtained by interchanging the roles of \hat{p}_1 and \hat{p}_2 — that is, varying \hat{p}_2 while keeping \hat{p}_1 fixed — are provided in Appendix Bi.

Fig 7: Plots comparing the EO, Wald, and Newcombe CI bounds with respect to \hat{p}_1 for various fixed values of \hat{p}_2 . Both sample sizes are set to $n_1 = n_2 = 20$, with the significance level fixed at $\alpha = 5\%$.

Figures 7 and 11 (Appendix i) illustrate that when either \hat{p}_1 or \hat{p}_2 is near the boundaries (0.01 or 0.99), Wald’s interval performs poorly, often producing overly narrow or even invalid bounds due to its reliance on the variance approximation. Newcombe’s interval, based on Wilson’s score limits, provides more reliable coverage but exhibits some irregularities near the extremes. In contrast, the proposed EO interval remains smooth, symmetric, and strictly bounded within $[0, 1]$, reflecting greater robustness and numerical stability in these regions. For moderate values of \hat{p}_1 and \hat{p}_2 (e.g., 0.25 or 0.75), the three methods yield comparable intervals; however, Wald’s remains slightly overconfident, while the EO and Newcombe intervals achieve better nominal coverage.

We next examine how the EO and Wald, as well as the EO and Newcombe, CIs differ across the (\hat{p}_1, \hat{p}_2) domain.

Fig 8: The orderings of the EO and Wald, as well as the EO and Newcombe, CI bounds – along with their corresponding regions in the (\hat{p}_1, \hat{p}_2) domain – are illustrated for $n_1 = n_2 = 20$ and $\alpha = 5\%$. Here, L_{EO} and U_{EO} , L_{Wald} and U_{Wald} , and L_{NC} and U_{NC} denote the lower and upper bounds of the EO, Wald, and Newcombe CIs, respectively.

Figure 8 shows that the EO and Wald intervals exhibit substantial variability: Wald’s bounds may lie above, below, within, or even encompass those of the EO interval, reflecting the instability of its approximation. In contrast, the EO and Newcombe intervals display a more consistent relationship, with Newcombe’s bounds generally contained within those of the EO interval and tending to underestimate the feasible parameter region.

We next overlay the EO, Wald, and Newcombe bounds on the set Λ to examine how each method compares with the true parameter coverage region.

Fig 9: Plots comparing the EO, Wald, and Newcombe CI bounds with respect to the set Λ for selected values of \hat{p}_1 and \hat{p}_2 . Both sample sizes are fixed at $n_1 = n_2 = 20$, with the significance level set to $\alpha = 5\%$.

Across all cases, Figure 9 shows that the EO intervals remain well-behaved around the set Λ . In contrast, Wald's intervals deviate markedly, often shifting upward or downward due to inherent approximation errors. Newcombe's intervals perform better than Wald's, offering improved coverage yet still underestimating the extent of Λ , which renders them less accurate and insufficiently conservative.

Overall, the EO method yields the most stable and accurate bounds, effectively capturing the true confidence structure while avoiding the distortions present in the other two methods.

4. Error Analysis. The elliptically optimal (EO) confidence interval (CI), as noted before, represents a conservative estimate of the true CI of p . This introduces an error, which can be quantified by comparing the probabilities associated with the EO CI and the true CI. Formally, since $\Lambda \subseteq \Gamma$ then:

$$\mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Gamma) \geq \mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Lambda).$$

Accordingly, the EO CI error is defined as

$$\text{Error} = \mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Gamma) - \mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Lambda) \geq 0.$$

Before turning to the results of our analysis, we first introduce some key quantities.

Definition 2. For $n_1 > 0$, $n_2 > 0$, $z > 0$, and $p \in [-1, 1]$, let $L_1^*, L_2^*, U_1^*, U_2^*$ and V_4, V_2, V_3, V_1 be scalars defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} L_1^* &= p - z \sqrt{\frac{|p|(1-|p|)}{m}}, & U_1^* &= p + z \sqrt{\frac{|p|(1-|p|)}{m}}, \\ L_2^* &= p - \frac{z}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(n+m)^2 - 4nmp^2}{nm(n+m)}}, & U_2^* &= p + \frac{z}{2} \sqrt{\frac{(n+m)^2 - 4nmp^2}{nm(n+m)}}, \\ V_1 &= -\frac{n+m}{2n} - \frac{z}{2n} \sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}}, & V_2 &= -\frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n} \sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}}, \\ V_3 &= \frac{n+m}{2n} - \frac{z}{2n} \sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}}, & V_4 &= \frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n} \sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4. *The scalars in definition 2 follow the following order, for $n_1, n_2, z > 0$ and $p \in [-1, 1]$,*

- $L_2^* \leq L_1^* \leq U_1^* \leq U_2^*$
- $V_1 \leq \min(V_2, V_3) \leq \max(V_2, V_3) \leq V_4$

PROOF. The proof proceeds analogously to that of Proposition 3 and is therefore omitted. \square

Since $\mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Lambda) \approx 1 - \alpha$ (Equation (8)), then calculating the error reduces to evaluating $\mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Gamma)$. To this end, we invert each case in Table 1, Theorem 1, producing intervals for the random variable \hat{p} . The probability can then be computed by knowing n_1, n_2, z , and p . The following theorem summarizes the results of this inversion.

Theorem 2. *The intervals for \hat{p} , corresponding to each of the six cases in Table 1, alongside their conditions are given as:*

TABLE 2
Interval bounds for \hat{p} with the corresponding conditions on p and z .

	Intervals of \hat{p}	Condition	
		p	z
(1)	$\max(V_4, L_1^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, U_1^*)$	$\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p \leq 1$	$0 < z \leq S_1$
(2)	(a) $\max(-1, V_3) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, V_2, U_1^*)$	$-1 \leq p < -\frac{n+m}{2n}$	$z \geq T_3$
		$-\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p \leq -\frac{1}{3}$	$z \geq S_2$
	(b) $\max(-1, V_3) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, V_2)$	$-\frac{1}{3} < p < \frac{1}{3}$	$z \geq S_2$
(2)	(c) $\max(-1, V_3, L_1^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, V_2)$	$\frac{1}{3} \leq p \leq \frac{n+m}{2n}$	$z \geq S_2$
		$\frac{n+m}{2n} < p \leq 1$	$z \geq T_3$
(3)	$\max(-1, L_1^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(V_1, U_1^*)$	$-1 \leq p \leq -\frac{n+m}{2n}$	$0 < z \leq S_1$
(4)	$\max(-1, V_1, L_2^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(- V_3 , U_1^*)$	$-1 \leq p \leq -\frac{n+m}{2n}$	$T_2 < z < S_3$
		$-\frac{n+m}{2n} < p \leq 0$	$T_1 \leq z < S_3$
(5)	$\max(V_3 , L_1^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, V_4, U_2^*)$	$0 \leq p < \frac{n+m}{2n}$	$T_1 \leq z < S_3$
		$\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p \leq 1$	$T_2 < z < S_3$
(6)	$\max(V_2, L_2^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(V_3, U_2^*)$	$-\frac{n+m}{2n} < p < \frac{n+m}{2n}$	$0 < z < S_2$

Where

$$S_1 = \sqrt{\frac{m(n-m)}{n+m}}, \quad S_2 = \sqrt{\frac{m(n+m)}{n-m}}, \quad S_3 = (3n+m)\sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2-m^2}},$$

$$T_1 = \sqrt{\frac{(2n-m)(n+m)^3 - 4n^2m(n+m)p^2 - 2(n+m)^2\sqrt{n(n-m)}((n+m)^2 - 4nmp^2)}{m(n+m+2n|p|)^2}},$$

$$T_2 = \sqrt{\frac{nm\left(n+4n|p|(1-|p|) - 4\sqrt{(n^2-m^2)}|p|(1-|p|)\right) - m^3}{(n-m-2n|p|)^2}},$$

$$T_3 = (n+m+2n|p|)\sqrt{\frac{nm\left(n+4n|p|(1-|p|) - 4\sqrt{(n^2-m^2)}|p|(1-|p|)\right) - m^3}{(m^2-n^2(1-2|p|)^2)^2}}.$$

PROOF. The proof supporting Theorem 2 can be found in Appendix Av. \square

Remark 2. Similar to the observation in Remark 1, when $n = m$ the only viable cases in Table 2 are (4), (5), and (6). From (4) and (5), we get the point intervals $\hat{p} = -1$ and $\hat{p} = 1$, corresponding to the conditions $p = -1$, $z > 0$ and $p = 1$, $z > 0$, respectively. From (6), we obtain the interval $\max(-1, L_2^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, U_2^*)$ for $-1 < p < 1$ and $z > 0$.

Proposition 5. The bounds for z in Theorem 2 can be ordered as follows:
For any p in $[-1, 1]$:

- $S_1 \leq S_2 \leq S_3$
- $T_1 \leq T_2 \leq T_3$
- $T_2 \leq S_2$

- $T_3 \leq S_3$

For $-\frac{n+m}{2n} < p < \frac{n+m}{2n}$:

- $T_3 \leq S_2 \leq S_3$

For $-1 \leq p \leq -\frac{n+m}{2n}$ or $\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p \leq 1$:

- $T_1 \leq T_2 \leq S_1 \leq S_2 \leq T_3 \leq S_3$

PROOF. We omit the details since the proof parallels that of Proposition 3. \square

Corollary 3. *Looking at Theorem 2 in conjunction with Proposition 5, we see that several conditions in Table 2 overlap. In particular, the following ranges of p and z indicate where the six cases intersect:*

- Cases (2) and (4) in $-1 < p \leq -\frac{n+m}{2n}$, $T_3 \leq z < S_3$, and in $-\frac{n+m}{2n} < p \leq 0$, $S_2 \leq z < S_3$.
- Cases (3) and (4) in $-1 < p \leq -\frac{n+m}{2n}$, $T_2 < z \leq S_1$.
- Cases (4) and (6) in $-\frac{n+m}{2n} < p \leq 0$, $T_1 \leq z < S_2$.
- Cases (4) and (5) in $p = 0$, $T_1 \leq z < S_3$.
- Cases (5) and (6) in $0 \leq p < \frac{n+m}{2n}$, $T_1 \leq z < S_2$.
- Cases (1) and (5) in $\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p < 1$, $T_2 < z \leq S_1$.
- Cases (2) and (5) in $0 \leq p < \frac{n+m}{2n}$, $S_2 \leq z < S_3$, and in $\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p < 1$, $T_3 \leq z < S_3$.

Hence, the conditions on p and z in Table 2 are not mutually exclusive. This is natural, since the inversion for \hat{p} is non-unique and therefore does not define a proper function.

Remark 3. In cases where the conditions overlap — i.e., when they yield two distinct intervals, as described in Corollary 3 — the resulting interval for \hat{p} is defined as their union. The corresponding probability, $\mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Gamma)$, is then obtained by summing the probabilities of the two intervals. This addition is valid because the intervals are mutually exclusive. Their exclusivity follows from the fact that the six cases partition the domain of \hat{p} in a disjoint manner, as specified in the conditions of Theorem 1 and illustrated in Figure 6.

With these considerations in place, we can now explicitly calculate the error for several choices of inputs. All probabilities are computed under the assumption that \hat{p} is approximately normally distributed with mean p and variance $\frac{p_1(1-p_1)}{n_1} + \frac{p_2(1-p_2)}{n_2}$. Furthermore, to isolate the EO error from the error due to the normal approximation, we assume that the usual rule of thumb holds for n_1, n_2, p_1 , and p_2 . Specifically, we require that $n_1 p_1$, $n_1(1-p_1)$, $n_2 p_2$, and $n_2(1-p_2)$ are all greater than 5 (10 is sometimes used for stricter validity). Under these conditions, the approximation error from the normal distribution is negligible, so the analysis focuses solely on the EO error.

With these assumptions, we may replace the approximation in Equation (8) by equality:

$$\mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Lambda) = 1 - \alpha,$$

making the error expressible as:

$$\text{Error} = \mathbb{P}((p_1, p_2) \in \Gamma) - (1 - \alpha),$$

such that:

$$0 \leq \text{Error} \leq \alpha.$$

The following example presents error plots corresponding to different choices of the significance level α . The sample sizes are fixed at $n_1 = n_2 = 45$. Additional plots for the complementary cases $n_1 > n_2$ and $n_1 < n_2$ are provided in Appendix Bii and Appendix Biii, respectively.

Fig 10: Error plots over the parameter domain (p_1, p_2) for three significance levels α . Both sample sizes are fixed at $n_1 = n_2 = 45$.

From figures, 10, 12 (Appendix Bii), and 13 (Appendix Biii), we observe that the error fluctuates depending on the choice of inputs. Nevertheless, a general pattern emerges in its behavior: the error approximately reaches its minimum when

$$\beta_1 p_1 + \beta_2 p_2 = 1,$$

for some $\beta_1, \beta_2 > 0$. These coefficients are determined by the values of n_1 and n_2 . For example, when $n_1 = n_2$, the coefficients satisfy $\beta_1 = \beta_2 = 1$, and the error is minimized along the line $p_1 + p_2 = 1$. As we deviate from this valley — defined by the linear combination above — the error increases symmetrically in either direction, eventually reaching its maximum value α at the diagonal extremes of the pair (p_1, p_2) i.e. close to $(0, 0)$ and $(1, 1)$.

5. Conclusions. This study extends Wilson’s classical score interval to the two-population case through a geometric and optimization-based framework. By recognizing that the joint constraint on (p_1, p_2) forms an ellipse, we derived the elliptically optimal (EO) confidence interval as the range of all feasible values of the difference $p_1 - p_2$ under this ellipse. The EO interval thus represents a genuine bivariate analogue to Wilson’s univariate method — one that maintains interpretability, theoretical rigor, and numerical stability. Our results show that EO intervals are consistently conservative, ensuring coverage probabilities at least as large as the nominal level. Compared with Wald’s and Newcombe’s intervals, the EO bounds exhibit markedly superior performance across sample sizes, significance levels, and parameter configurations. Theoretical analysis and numerical illustrations further confirm that EO intervals maintain robustness at the boundaries of the parameter space and avoid the under-coverage commonly observed in traditional methods. Beyond offering a theoretically sound alternative, the EO framework provides a unified perspective that can be extended to more complex inferential problems involving constrained or multiple variables.

APPENDIX A: PROOFS

i. Proof of Proposition 1.

PROOF. We will prove both claims by contradiction.

First, for $\Lambda \neq \emptyset$: Suppose that, for some n_1, n_2, \hat{p} , and z , Λ is empty. That means for all (p_1, p_2) in $[0, 1]^2$ the equation of the ellipse is strictly greater than zero. Set $p_2 = 1 - p_1$ which includes the line segment that passes through the unit square as an opposite diagonal. With this in place, the equation of the ellipse in Equation (8) yields the following simplified expression:

$$\left(4 + \frac{(n_1 + n_2)z^2}{n_1 n_2}\right) p_1^2 - \left(4(1 + \hat{p}) + \frac{(n_1 + n_2)z^2}{n_1 n_2}\right) p_1 + (1 + \hat{p})^2.$$

Equating the above expression to zero and solving for its roots yields

$$r_1 = \frac{(n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 4n_1 n_2(1 + \hat{p}) - z\sqrt{(n_1 + n_2)((n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 4n_1 n_2(1 - \hat{p}^2))}}{2((n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 4n_1 n_2)},$$

and,

$$r_2 = \frac{(n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 4n_1 n_2(1 + \hat{p}) + z\sqrt{(n_1 + n_2)((n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 4n_1 n_2(1 - \hat{p}^2))}}{2((n_1 + n_2)z^2 + 4n_1 n_2)}.$$

The roots r_1 and r_2 are real, distinct, and satisfy $r_1 < r_2$. A straightforward calculus argument shows that r_1 is minimized at $\hat{p} = -1$ and r_2 is maximized at $\hat{p} = 1$. From this observation, simple algebra implies

$$0 \leq r_1, \text{ and, } r_2 \leq 1.$$

Hence $0 \leq r_1 < r_2 \leq 1$. Since the leading coefficient, $\left(4 + \frac{(n_1 + n_2)z^2}{n_1 n_2}\right)$ is positive, it follows that there exists (p_1, p_2) , with $p_2 = 1 - p_1$ and $p_1 \in [0, 1]$, such that the equation of the ellipse is less than zero. This is in direct contradiction with our original assumption. Thus the set Λ is always non-empty.

Second, for $\Lambda \subset \Omega$: Suppose, for the sake of contradiction, that $\Lambda = \Omega$ for some choice of n_1, n_2, \hat{p} , and z . Then, by construction, the quadratic form

$$Ap_1^2 + Bp_1 p_2 + Cp_2^2 + Dp_1 + Ep_2 + F \geq 0.$$

must be non-negative for all boundary points (p_1, p_2) of the unit square, and strictly positive for every point outside the unit square.

To analyze this, first set $p_2 = 0$ and then $p_1 = 0$. This leads to two one-dimensional quadratic inequalities:

$$\left(1 + \frac{z^2}{n_1}\right) p_1^2 + \left(-2\hat{p} - \frac{z^2}{n_1}\right) p_1 + \hat{p}^2 \geq 0, \text{ for all } p_1 \in \mathbb{R},$$

$$\left(1 + \frac{z^2}{n_2}\right) p_2^2 + \left(2\hat{p} - \frac{z^2}{n_2}\right) p_2 + \hat{p}^2 \geq 0, \text{ for all } p_2 \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Solving the corresponding quadratic equations yields the roots

$$r_{11} = \frac{n_1 \hat{p} + z^2/2}{n_1 + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4n_1 \hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}}{2(n_1 + z^2)},$$

$$r_{12} = \frac{n_1 \hat{p} + z^2/2}{n_1 + z^2} + \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4n_1 \hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}}{2(n_1 + z^2)},$$

for the first, and

$$r_{21} = \frac{-n_2\hat{p} + z^2/2}{n_2 + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 - 4n_2\hat{p}(1 + \hat{p})}}{2(n_2 + z^2)},$$

$$r_{22} = \frac{-n_2\hat{p} + z^2/2}{n_2 + z^2} + \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 - 4n_2\hat{p}(1 + \hat{p})}}{2(n_2 + z^2)}.$$

for the second.

Furthermore, elementary algebraic arguments show that the roots satisfy one of the following orderings:

$$0 \leq r_{11} < r_{12} \leq 1, \text{ and, } 0 \leq r_{21} \leq r_{22} \leq 1,$$

or

$$0 \leq r_{11} \leq r_{12} \leq 1, \text{ and, } 0 \leq r_{21} < r_{22} \leq 1.$$

Since both inequalities correspond to quadratic polynomials with positive leading coefficients, each polynomial attains negative values between its roots. Therefore, there exists either $p_1 \in (r_{11}, r_{12})$ or $p_2 \in (r_{21}, r_{22})$ such that

$$\left(1 + \frac{z^2}{n_1}\right)p_1^2 + \left(-2\hat{p} - \frac{z^2}{n_1}\right)p_1 + \hat{p}^2 < 0,$$

or

$$\left(1 + \frac{z^2}{n_2}\right)p_2^2 + \left(2\hat{p} - \frac{z^2}{n_2}\right)p_2 + \hat{p}^2 < 0.$$

This contradicts the original assumption that the quadratic form is non-negative everywhere. Hence, it follows that $\Lambda \neq \Omega$, and therefore $\Lambda \subset \Omega$.

The proof can proceed similarly if instead of picking $p_2 = 0$ and $p_1 = 0$, we pick $p_2 = 1$ and $p_1 = 1$ and then following the same arguments to arrive at the contradiction.

Moreover, this result implies the existence of two distinct points (p_1, p_2) , one lying either in $(0, 1) \times (-\infty, 0)$ or in $(-\infty, 0) \times (0, 1)$ and another lying either in $(0, 1) \times (1, \infty)$ or in $(1, \infty) \times (0, 1)$ such that

$$Ap_1^2 + Bp_1p_2 + Cp_2^2 + Dp_1 + Ep_2 + F < 0.$$

□

ii. Proof of Proposition 2.

PROOF. We will prove the case

$$\left(-\frac{1}{2}, 0\right] \times \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right),$$

as the remaining pieces follow by the same reasoning.

First, note that each of p_1^c and p_2^c lies strictly between $-\frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{3}{2}$. Now, suppose $-\frac{1}{2} < p_1^c \leq 0$ then:

$$-1 < \frac{n_1\hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2} \leq -\frac{1}{2},$$

which can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} -1 < \frac{n_1 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2} &\implies -n_1 - n_2 - n_1 \hat{p} < z^2, \\ \frac{n_1 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2} \leq -\frac{1}{2} &\implies z^2 \leq -n_1 - n_2 - 2n_1 \hat{p}, \end{aligned}$$

and hence

$$-n_1 - n_2 - n_1 \hat{p} < z^2 \leq -n_1 - n_2 - 2n_1 \hat{p}.$$

Since $z > 0$ and $-1 \leq \hat{p} \leq 1$, then we obtain $-n_1 - n_2 - n_1 \hat{p} < 0$, which forces

$$0 < z^2 \leq -n_1 - n_2 - 2n_1 \hat{p}.$$

For this inequality to be consistent, the upper bound must be strictly positive, i.e.

$$-1 \leq \hat{p} < -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2n_1}.$$

Moreover, because $-1 < -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2n_1}$, it follows that $n_1 > n_2$.

Next, consider the quantity from the second coordinate:

$$-\frac{n_2 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2}.$$

Using the restrictions derived above, we obtain

$$-\frac{n_2 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2} < -\frac{n_2 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2} \leq \frac{n_2}{n_1 + n_2} < \frac{1}{2},$$

and,

$$-\frac{n_2 \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2} \geq \frac{-n_2 \hat{p}}{-2n_1 \hat{p}} = \frac{n_2}{2n_1} > 0.$$

Finally, adding $\frac{1}{2}$ to both bounds yields

$$\frac{1}{2} < p_2^c < 1.$$

Thus $(p_1^c, p_2^c) \in \left(\left(-\frac{1}{2}, 0 \right] \times \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1 \right) \right)$, as required. \square

iii. Proof of Proposition 3.

PROOF. From the definition of n_1, n_2, \hat{p} , and z , the orders $L_1 \leq U_1, L_2 \leq U_2$ and $L_3 \leq U_3$ follow. We only, therefore, need to check the following inequalities $L_3 \leq L_2, U_2 \leq L_1$, and $U_1 \leq U_3$. We will first show that $U_2 \leq L_1$.

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 - U_2 &= \frac{z^2}{m + z^2} - \frac{z}{2(m + z^2)} \left(\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})} + \sqrt{z^2 - 4m\hat{p}(1 + \hat{p})} \right), \\ &\geq \frac{z^2}{m + z^2} - \frac{z}{2(m + z^2)} \left(\sqrt{z^2} + \sqrt{z^2} \right), \\ &= \frac{z^2}{m + z^2} - \frac{2z^2}{2(m + z^2)}, \\ &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

The inequality above follows since the maximum of $\left(\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})} + \sqrt{z^2 - 4m\hat{p}(1 + \hat{p})}\right)$ with respect to \hat{p} is attained at $\hat{p} = 0$.

The proofs of $L_3 \leq L_2$ and $U_1 \leq U_3$ rely on the same underlying argument. Hence, it suffices to establish $L_3 \leq L_2$, as the inequality $U_1 \leq U_3$ follows by an analogous reasoning.

For $L_3 \leq L_2$ to hold, the square-root terms must be real, which imposes the following feasibility conditions on \hat{p} and z : $-1 \leq \hat{p} \leq 1$ and $z > \sqrt{8m}$, or $-1 \leq \hat{p} \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(-1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{z^2}{m}}\right)$ and $0 < z \leq \sqrt{8m}$. Next, let's find the roots of

$$L_2 - L_3 = 0$$

with respect to the variable \hat{p} . To do so, we will need to square the equation two times to get rid of the square roots, and then group the similar terms together. We finally get:

$$a_1\hat{p}^4 + a_2\hat{p}^3 + a_3\hat{p}^2 + a_4\hat{p} + a_5 = 0,$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 &= \frac{n^2 z^4}{(m + z^2)^2 (n + m + z^2)^2}, \\ a_2 &= \frac{2nz^4(m + n)}{(m + z^2)^2 (n + m + z^2)^2}, \\ a_3 &= \frac{z^4(n + m)(3m^2 + m(3n + z^2) - nz^2)}{2m(m + z^2)^2 (n + m + z^2)^2}, \\ a_4 &= \frac{z^4(n + m)^2(m^2 + m(n + z^2) - nz^2)}{2nm(m + z^2)^2 (n + m + z^2)^2}, \\ a_5 &= \frac{z^4(n + m)^2(m^2 + m(n + z^2) - nz^2)^2}{16n^2m^2(m + z^2)^2 (n + m + z^2)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Solving the quartic equation yields the following two roots each with multiplicity of 2:

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= -\frac{m^2 + mn + z\sqrt{m(n^2 - m^2)}}{2nm}, \\ r_2 &= \frac{-m^2 - mn + z\sqrt{m(n^2 - m^2)}}{2nm}. \end{aligned}$$

To establish the inequality $L_3 \leq L_2$, we need to verify that $L_2 - L_3$, viewed as a function of \hat{p} , remains positive across the three relevant regions: (1) $\hat{p} < r_1$, (2) $r_1 < \hat{p} < r_2$, and (3) $\hat{p} > r_2$. We must also respect the restrictions on \hat{p} and z introduced earlier. To this end, it suffices to evaluate $L_2 - L_3$ at representative points within each region: $\hat{p} = -1$, $\hat{p} = \frac{r_1 + r_2}{2} = -\frac{n + m}{2n}$, and $\hat{p} = \min\left(1, \frac{1}{2} \left(-1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{z^2}{m}}\right)\right)$.

Substituting these values, we then repeat the procedure on the equation $L_2 - L_3 = 0$, this time with respect to z . Without delving into more details, this analysis yields only imaginary roots in all three cases. And, for any feasible z — whether above or below $\sqrt{8m}$ — the expression $L_2 - L_3$ remains positive. Consequently, the inequality $L_3 \leq L_2$ always holds for all appropriate choices of n_1, n_2, \hat{p} , and z . This completes the proof. \square

iv. Proof of Theorem 1.

PROOF. We establish the lower bound, corresponding to the minimization component of the CI; the derivation of the upper bound proceeds analogously. The analysis relies on the method of Lagrange multipliers, in particular the Karush–Kuhn–Tucker (KKT) conditions [6, 4, 5].

By stationarity and complementary slackness we get the following system of equations:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + \mu_1 (2Ap_1 + Bp_2 + D) - \mu_2 + \mu_3 &= 0, \\ -1 + \mu_1 (Bp_1 + 2Cp_2 + E) - \mu_4 + \mu_5 &= 0, \\ \mu_1 (Ap_1^2 + Bp_1p_2 + Cp_2 + Dp_1 + Ep_2 + F) &= 0, \\ \mu_2(-p_1) &= 0, \\ \mu_3(p_1 - 1) &= 0, \\ \mu_4(-p_2) &= 0, \\ \mu_5(p_2 - 1) &= 0. \end{aligned}$$

Here, A, B, C, D, E , and F are as defined in Equation (8), and μ_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$ denote the KKT multipliers. Solving the system yields multiple candidate solutions. Imposing the dual feasibility condition $\mu_i \geq 0$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 5\}$, together with the constraints on the inputs $n_1, n_2, z > 0$ and $\hat{p} \in [-1, 1]$, reduces the set to the following admissible solutions:

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \quad \mu_1 &= \frac{n_2}{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4n_2\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}}, \mu_2 = 0, \mu_3 = -\frac{z^2(n_1 + \mu_1(n_1 + n_2 - 2n_1\hat{p} + z^2))}{n_1(n_2 + z^2)}, \\ \mu_4 &= 0, \mu_5 = 0, p_1^* = 1, p_2^* = \frac{1}{2} \left(2 + \frac{1 + \mu_3}{\mu_1} + \frac{z^2}{n_1} - 2\hat{p} \right), \\ (2) \quad \mu_1 &= \frac{n_2}{z\sqrt{z^2 - 4n_2\hat{p}(1+\hat{p})}}, \mu_2 = -\frac{z^2(-n_1 + \mu_1(n_1 + n_2 + 2n_1\hat{p} + z^2))}{n_1(n_2 + z^2)}, \mu_3 = 0, \\ \mu_4 &= 0, \mu_5 = 0, p_1^* = 0, p_2^* = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1 - \mu_2}{\mu_1} - \frac{z^2}{n_1} - 2\hat{p} \right), \\ (3) \quad \mu_1 &= \frac{n_1}{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4n_1\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}}, \mu_2 = 0, \mu_3 = 0, \mu_4 = -\frac{z^2(n_2 + \mu_1(n_1 + n_2 - 2n_2\hat{p} + z^2))}{n_2(n_1 + z^2)}, \\ \mu_5 &= 0, p_1^* = \frac{1}{2} \left(-\frac{1 + \mu_4}{\mu_1} - \frac{z^2}{n_2} + 2\hat{p} \right), p_2^* = 0, \\ (4) \quad \mu_1 &= \frac{n_1}{z\sqrt{z^2 - 4n_1\hat{p}(1+\hat{p})}}, \mu_2 = 0, \mu_3 = 0, \mu_4 = 0, \\ \mu_5 &= -\frac{z^2(-n_2 + \mu_1(n_1 + n_2 + 2n_2\hat{p} + z^2))}{n_2(n_1 + z^2)}, p_1^* = \frac{1}{2} \left(2 - \frac{1 - \mu_5}{\mu_1} + \frac{z^2}{n_2} + 2\hat{p} \right), p_2^* = 1, \end{aligned}$$

$$(5) \quad \mu_1 = \frac{\sqrt{n_1 n_2 (n_1 + n_2)}}{z \sqrt{(n_1 + n_2)^2 + (n_1 + n_2) z^2 - 4 n_1 n_2 \hat{p}^2}}, \quad \mu_2 = 0, \quad \mu_3 = 0, \quad \mu_4 = 0, \quad \mu_5 = 0,$$

$$p_1^* = \frac{-n_1 + \mu_1 (n_1 + n_2 + 2 n_1 \hat{p} + z^2)}{2 \mu_1 (n_1 + n_2 + z^2)}, \quad p_2^* = \frac{n_2 + \mu_1 (n_1 + n_2 - 2 n_2 \hat{p} + z^2)}{2 \mu_1 (n_1 + n_2 + z^2)}.$$

From the five candidate solution sets, we further impose primal feasibility by verifying that $(p_1, p_2) \in \mathbf{\Lambda}$, in addition to the dual feasibility conditions. This yields the following lower bounds for p , each accompanied by its corresponding validity conditions:

$$(1) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{n_2 \hat{p} + z^2/2}{n_2 + z^2} - \frac{z \sqrt{z^2 + 4 n_2 \hat{p} (1 - \hat{p})}}{2 (n_2 + z^2)},$$

$$n_1 > n_2, \quad \frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_1} < \hat{p} \leq 1, \quad 0 < z \leq (2 n_1 \hat{p} - (n_1 + n_2)) \sqrt{\frac{n_2}{n_1^2 - n_2^2}},$$

$$(2) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{n_2 \hat{p} - z^2/2}{n_2 + z^2} - \frac{z \sqrt{z^2 - 4 n_2 \hat{p} (1 + \hat{p})}}{2 (n_2 + z^2)},$$

$$n_1 \geq n_2, \quad -1 \leq \hat{p} \leq -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_1}, \quad z > 0, \quad \text{or,}$$

$$n_1 > n_2, \quad -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_1} < \hat{p} \leq 1, \quad z \geq |2 n_1 \hat{p} + (n_1 + n_2)| \sqrt{\frac{n_2}{n_1^2 - n_2^2}},$$

$$(3) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{n_1 \hat{p} + z^2/2}{n_1 + z^2} - \frac{z \sqrt{z^2 + 4 n_1 \hat{p} (1 - \hat{p})}}{2 (n_1 + z^2)},$$

$$n_2 > n_1, \quad \frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_2} < \hat{p} \leq 1, \quad 0 < z \leq (2 n_2 \hat{p} - (n_1 + n_2)) \sqrt{\frac{n_1}{n_2^2 - n_1^2}},$$

$$(4) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{n_1 \hat{p} - z^2/2}{n_1 + z^2} - \frac{z \sqrt{z^2 - 4 n_1 \hat{p} (1 + \hat{p})}}{2 (n_1 + z^2)},$$

$$n_2 \geq n_1, \quad -1 \leq \hat{p} \leq -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_2}, \quad z > 0, \quad \text{or,}$$

$$n_2 > n_1, \quad -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_2} < \hat{p} \leq 1, \quad z \geq |2 n_2 \hat{p} + (n_1 + n_2)| \sqrt{\frac{n_1}{n_2^2 - n_1^2}},$$

$$(5) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{(n_1 + n_2) \hat{p}}{n_1 + n_2 + z^2} - \frac{z \sqrt{(n_1 + n_2) z^2 - 4 n_1 n_2 \hat{p}^2 + (n_1 + n_2)^2}}{2 (n_1 + n_2 + z^2)} \sqrt{\frac{n_1 + n_2}{n_1 n_2}},$$

$$n_1 > n_2, \quad -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_1} < \hat{p} \leq \frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_1}, \quad 0 < z < |2 n_1 \hat{p} + (n_1 + n_2)| \sqrt{\frac{n_2}{n_1^2 - n_2^2}}, \quad \text{or,}$$

$$n_1 > n_2, \quad \frac{n_1 + n_2}{2 n_1} < \hat{p} \leq 1, \quad (2 n_1 \hat{p} - (n_1 + n_2)) \sqrt{\frac{n_2}{n_1^2 - n_2^2}} < z < |2 n_1 \hat{p} + (n_1 + n_2)| \sqrt{\frac{n_2}{n_1^2 - n_2^2}}, \quad \text{or,}$$

$$n_1 = n_2, \quad -1 < \hat{p} \leq 1, \quad z > 0, \quad \text{or,}$$

$$n_2 > n_1, -\frac{n_1 + n_2}{2n_2} < \hat{p} \leq \frac{n_1 + n_2}{2n_2}, 0 < z < |2n_2\hat{p} + (n_1 + n_2)| \sqrt{\frac{n_1}{n_2^2 - n_1^2}}, \text{ or,}$$

$$n_2 > n_1, \frac{n_1 + n_2}{2n_2} < \hat{p} \leq 1, (2n_2\hat{p} - (n_1 + n_2)) \sqrt{\frac{n_1}{n_2^2 - n_1^2}} < z < |2n_2\hat{p} + (n_1 + n_2)| \sqrt{\frac{n_1}{n_2^2 - n_1^2}}.$$

By utilizing the notations, $n = \max(n_1, n_2)$ and $m = \min(n_1, n_2)$, we can combine (1) and (3), (2) and (4), and the conditions of (5), and compactly write the five solutions as:

$$(1) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{m\hat{p} + z^2/2}{m + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1 - \hat{p})}}{2(m + z^2)},$$

$$\frac{n + m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq 1, 0 < z \leq (2n\hat{p} - (n + m)) \sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2 - m^2}},$$

$$(2) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{m\hat{p} - z^2/2}{m + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 - 4m\hat{p}(1 + \hat{p})}}{2(m + z^2)},$$

$$-1 \leq \hat{p} \leq -\frac{n + m}{2n}, z > 0, \text{ or,}$$

$$-\frac{n + m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq 1, z \geq |2n\hat{p} + (n + m)| \sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2 - m^2}},$$

$$(3) \quad p_1^* - p_2^* = \frac{(n + m)\hat{p}}{n + m + z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{(n + m)z^2 - 4nm\hat{p}^2 + (n + m)^2}}{2(n + m + z^2)} \sqrt{\frac{n + m}{nm}},$$

$$-\frac{n + m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq \frac{n + m}{2n}, 0 < z < |2n\hat{p} + (n + m)| \sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2 - m^2}}, \text{ or,}$$

$$\frac{n + m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq 1, (2n\hat{p} - (n + m)) \sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2 - m^2}} < z < |2n\hat{p} + (n + m)| \sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2 - m^2}},$$

In these compact forms, it is understood that when $n = m$ we only retain the conditions consistent with this case. For instance, the inequality $-\frac{n + m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq \frac{n + m}{2n} \implies -1 < \hat{p} \leq 1$ remains valid, whereas $\frac{n + m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq 1 \implies 1 < \hat{p} \leq 1$ does not. Moreover, any bounds on z that involve the term $\sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2 - m^2}}$ are interpreted as infinite unless multiplied by zero then it is defined to be zero.

Finally, applying the same procedure to obtain the maximum, i.e., the upper bound of p , we identify the intersections of the feasibility conditions to determine which lower bounds align with which upper bounds. This leads to the results summarized in Table 1, thereby completing the proof. \square

v. Proof of Theorem 2.

PROOF. Our goal is to derive an interval for \hat{p} , given the known input n_1, n_2, p and z , across the six cases listed in Table 1. The derivation proceeds by inverting the inequalities in each case to obtain the bounds for \hat{p} . Since the procedure is identical for all six cases, we present the detailed proof only for case (1); the remaining cases follow analogously.

From Table 1, we have:

$$L_1 \leq p \leq U_1,$$

with:

$$\frac{n+m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq 1, \quad 0 < z \leq R_1$$

For the first inequality, let us write it in terms of \hat{p} by manipulating the bounds.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{m\hat{p} + z^2/2}{m+z^2} - \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}}{2(m+z^2)} \leq p \leq \frac{m\hat{p} + z^2/2}{m+z^2} + \frac{z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}}{2(m+z^2)}, \\ \implies & -z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})} \leq 2(m+z^2)p - (2m\hat{p} + z^2) \leq z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}, \\ \implies & |2(m+z^2)p - (2m\hat{p} + z^2)| \leq z\sqrt{z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}, \\ \implies & (2(m+z^2)p - (2m\hat{p} + z^2))^2 \leq z^2(z^2 + 4m\hat{p}(1-\hat{p})), \\ \implies & 4m(m+z^2)\hat{p}^2 - 8mp(m+z^2)\hat{p} + 4p(m+z^2)(p(m+z^2) - z^2) \leq 0, \\ (1) \implies & p - z\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{m}} \leq \hat{p} \leq p + z\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{m}}. \end{aligned}$$

The last implication follows since the quadratic equation has a positive leading coefficient i.e. $4m(m+z^2) > 0$.

We apply the same procedure for the second set of inequalities.

$$\begin{aligned} (2) \quad & \frac{n+m}{2n} < \hat{p} \leq 1, \\ & 0 < z \leq R_1, \\ \implies & 0 < z \leq (2n|\hat{p}| - (n+m))\sqrt{\frac{m}{n^2 - m^2}}, \\ (3) \implies & \frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n}\sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}} \leq \hat{p}. \end{aligned}$$

Combining (2) and (3) we get:

$$(4) \quad \frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n}\sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}} \leq \hat{p} \leq 1.$$

Then further combining (1) and (4) we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max\left(\frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n}\sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}}, p - z\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{m}}\right) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min\left(1, p + z\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{m}}\right), \\ (5) \implies & \max(V_4, L_1^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, U_1^*). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the conditions on p and z are recovered by verifying that (5) is well defined. In other words, we must ensure that the intersection of (2) with (3), and of (1) with (4), is non-empty.

Since $\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq \frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n}\sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}}$, then to verify (2) and (3), we need to only check if

$$\frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n}\sqrt{\frac{n^2 - m^2}{m}} \leq 1.$$

This happens if and only if

$$0 < z \leq \sqrt{\frac{m(n-m)}{n+m}},$$

$$\implies 0 < z \leq S_1.$$

Next, between (1) and (4), we must ensure that

$$p - z\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{m}} \leq 1 \leq p + z\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{m}}, \text{ and,}$$

$$\frac{n+m}{2n} + \frac{z}{2n}\sqrt{\frac{n^2-m^2}{m}} \leq p + z\sqrt{\frac{p(1-p)}{m}} \leq 1.$$

From the first and the second condition, we get $\frac{m}{m+z^2} \leq p \leq 1$, $z > 0$ and $\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p \leq \frac{m}{m+z^2}$, $0 < z \leq \sqrt{\frac{m(n-m)}{m+n}}$, respectively. Putting all of the conditions together, along with the interval of \hat{p} we have:

$$\max(V_4, L_1^*) \leq \hat{p} \leq \min(1, U_1^*),$$

$$\frac{n+m}{2n} \leq p \leq 1, \quad 0 < z \leq S_1.$$

Which is result (1) in Table 1. This completes the proof. □

APPENDIX B: ADDITIONAL FIGURES

i. EO and Wald CI comparison.

Fig 11: Different plots of the EO, Wald's and Newcombe's bounds with respect to \hat{p}_2 across various choices of \hat{p}_1 . n_1 and n_2 are both set to 20 while α is fixed to 5%.

ii. Error plot when $n_1 > n_2$.

Fig 12: Error plots over the parameter domain (p_1, p_2) for three significance levels α . The sample sizes are fixed at $n_1 = 60$ and $n_2 = 30$.

iii. Error plot when $n_1 < n_2$.

Fig 13: Error plots over the parameter domain (p_1, p_2) for three significance levels α . The sample sizes are fixed at $n_1 = 30$ and $n_2 = 60$.

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